

A framework for standardised characterisation of bulk material handling properties of planetary regolith simulants

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Abstract

Planetary regolith simulants are widely used to support the development of surface systems for exploration, construction, and in-situ resource utilisation. While their geotechnical and physicochemical properties are already well documented, the characterisation of bulk material handling properties critical to storage, conveying, excavation, and processing operations remains fragmented and largely non standardised. As a result, experimental data are often difficult to compare across studies, simulant batches, and testing facilities, limiting the transferability of findings to mission relevant scenarios.

This paper critically reviews existing approaches used to characterise the bulk handling behaviour of planetary regolith simulants, drawing on established practices from the bulk solids handling, powder technology, and particulate materials communities. Key challenges include the sensitivity of regolith simulants to particle size distribution, shape, surface texture, as well as inconsistencies in test selection, sample preparation, and data reporting.

Building on this analysis, the paper proposes a structured pathway for the standardised characterisation of bulk-material-handling properties of planetary regolith simulants. The framework outlines priority properties, appropriate test methods, and reporting protocols necessary to support reproducible, comparable, and application relevant data generation. The proposed approach aims to bridge the gap between planetary science and bulk solids engineering, providing a foundation for improved simulant qualification and more robust design of regolith-handling systems for future planetary missions.

Keywords:

Materials handling; lunar; granular materials, bulk materials; reduced gravity; validation; payload; lunar lander; mission

1 Introduction and context

The renewed global interest in lunar and planetary exploration, driven by both governmental space agencies and commercial stakeholders, has significantly accelerated research into surface operations beyond Earth [1,2]. Central to these efforts is in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU), which seeks to reduce mission cost and risk by exploiting locally available materials for construction, life support, and propellant production [3]. Consequently, the development and use of representative regolith simulants have become indispensable for experimental research, technology development, and system validation.

To date, the development of these simulants has primarily focused on reproducing chemical composition, mineralogy, and spectroscopic characteristics [4]. While these properties are essential for planetary science, they provide only a partial representation of the challenges encountered during surface operations. Dynamic bulk material handling behaviour-governing excavation, storage, transport, and processing-has received comparatively limited and inconsistent attention, introducing substantial uncertainty into engineering design decisions [5].

At present, the characterisation of bulk material handling properties for regolith simulants remains

fragmented and largely non-standardised [6]. Test methods, sample preparation procedures, and reporting practices vary significantly between studies and institutions [7,8,9,10]. As a result, simulants are frequently treated as poorly documented “black box” materials, with limited transparency regarding their handling behaviour or applicability to specific operational scenarios. This lack of standardisation impedes cross-institutional collaboration and leads to duplicated development efforts.

There is a clear and pressing requirement for a standardised classification and testing protocol specifically focused on the dynamic bulk-material-handling characteristics of planetary regolith simulants. Such a protocol should prioritise test methods established within the bulk solids handling community, while remaining practical and reproducible through the use of commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) laboratory equipment.

In this paper, an initial standardised protocol is proposed for characterising the dynamic bulk material-handling properties of lunar and planetary regolith simulants. A suite of eight representative materials is tested using readily available commercial equipment, with an emphasis on repeatability and transparency. The resulting data are presented in a structured, catalogue-style format intended to facilitate meaningful comparison

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across the scientific and engineering communities and provide a foundation for the robust design of future regolith handling systems. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 elaborates the case for and impact of a standardised regolith characterisation approach; Section 3 reviews established terrestrial methodologies; Section 4 details the proposed standardised protocol; Section 5 describes the data format; and Section 6 presents characterisation results for the selected suite of simulants. The paper concludes with a discussion on the route forward for community oversight and standardisation.

2 Need for bulk materials handling characterisation of planetary regolith simulants.

2.1 Background and context

Renewed international interest in lunar and Martian exploration has introduced ambitious objectives aimed at establishing a sustained, ultimately self-supporting human and robotic presence beyond Earth [11]. Achieving these goals will require extensive and continuous surface operations, including excavation, construction, geotechnical engineering, materials transport, in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU), and localised manufacturing [12]. A common and defining feature of all such activities is the need to interact with, manipulate, and process large quantities of granular planetary surface materials, collectively referred to as regolith.

From an engineering perspective, the interaction between machines and granular materials is governed by the principles of bulk materials handling, a mature discipline within terrestrial industries such as mining, minerals processing, agriculture, pharmaceuticals, and construction. On planetary surfaces, regolith must similarly be excavated, transferred, stored, metered, conveyed, compacted, and processed. While the large-scale deployment of these capabilities remains a future objective, a substantial and growing research and development (R&D) community is actively engaged in preparatory activities. These efforts are particularly pronounced for lunar applications, where regolith simulants are routinely employed to support laboratory experimentation, prototype development, and system-level validation.

Planetary regolith simulants, therefore, play a central role in enabling Earth-based investigation of extra-terrestrial surface operations. However, for these simulants to provide meaningful and reliable insights, their behaviour under relevant handling and loading conditions must be appropriately characterised and understood.

2.2 Current characterisation focus

Historically, the development and selection of planetary regolith simulants have prioritised a limited set of material attributes, most notably chemical composition, mineralogy, spectroscopic response, and particle-size distribution [13]. This emphasis reflects the origins of simulant development within the planetary science community, where early applications focused on correlating laboratory measurements with remote sensing

data. More recently, this focus has been reinforced by the requirements of ISRU research [14], where chemical and mineralogical fidelity is critical for process feasibility studies and reactor design.

Although some attention was paid to mechanical behaviour during the Apollo era, particularly regarding geotechnical properties such as bearing capacity and shear strength, this effort was largely motivated by the immediate need to ensure safe landings and surface mobility [15,16]. Once these concerns were successfully addressed, systematic investigation of bulk mechanical and handling properties received comparatively limited attention. As a result, the contemporary landscape of available lunar regolith simulants reflects this historical trajectory.

Existing datasets produced by major space agencies and research organisations, as well as commercial suppliers, typically provide extensive information on compositional and particle-scale characteristics but offer limited, inconsistent, or non-standardised data on properties directly relevant to bulk handling behaviour. Consequently, simulant selection is often driven by chemical or mineralogical considerations, even when the intended application primarily involves excavation, transport, or processing of bulk material [4, 6].

2.3 Emerging need for bulk materials handling characterisation

Looking ahead, many of the operations envisioned for sustained lunar surface activity—including regolith excavation for habitat construction, feedstock preparation for ISRU reactors, bulk transport for manufacturing processes, and general civil engineering works—are fundamentally governed by bulk materials handling behaviour. The success and reliability of these operations depend on material properties such as flowability, cohesiveness, compressibility, permeability, segregation tendency, and resistance to shear under low confining stresses.

To support the design, testing, and validation of relevant technologies, regolith simulants must therefore possess well-defined, application-relevant bulk-handling characteristics. Ideally, these properties should replicate, as closely as practicable, those of authentic lunar regolith to ensure the fidelity of Earth-based experimentation. However, a significant knowledge gap exists in this regard.

Direct experimental data on the bulk mechanical behaviour of genuine lunar regolith remain extremely limited. Ground-truth measurements are largely confined to observations and in-situ tests conducted during the Apollo and Luna missions, supplemented by sparse data from more recent robotic landers and rovers [17,18]. While substantial quantities of lunar regolith were returned to Earth during the Apollo programme, access to these materials is highly restricted, and only a small number of studies have examined their bulk mechanical behaviour [19,20]. Even these investigations have typically focused on relatively simple descriptors, such as angle of repose, offering limited insight into the complex behaviour relevant to modern bulk handling systems.

This scarcity of reference data, combined with the historical emphasis on compositional fidelity, has led to a

notable absence of systematically documented bulk-materials-handling properties for many widely used lunar regolith simulants. It is acknowledged that a fully representative simulation ultimately requires replication of the lunar operational environment, including reduced gravity, vacuum conditions, and electrostatic effects [21]. However, even under terrestrial laboratory conditions, the lack of standardised characterisation protocols significantly limits the interpretability and comparability of existing experimental results.

2.4 Risks and implications

The disconnect between the widespread use of regolith simulants in bulk handling-related research and the limited characterisation of their relevant mechanical properties introduces several important technical and programmatic risks. At present, simulants are frequently employed in the development and testing of excavation systems, handling equipment, and ISRU processes. Yet, there is no comprehensive or standardised data describing their bulk behaviour. In many cases, it remains unclear whether the simulants used provide a conservative, optimistic, or entirely unrepresentative approximation of actual lunar regolith behaviour.

This lack of validation undermines confidence in experimental outcomes and design decisions derived from simulant-based testing. Technologies and operational procedures developed under such conditions may exhibit unanticipated performance limitations, instability, or failure when exposed to genuine lunar materials. At a system level, this poses risks to mission safety, operational efficiency, and long-term sustainability. From a programmatic perspective, it may also lead to costly redesign cycles, delays, or the misallocation of resources.

Addressing these challenges requires a systematic, transparent approach to characterising the bulk-materials-handling properties of planetary regolith simulants. Establishing standardised test protocols and reporting practices would significantly enhance the reliability, comparability, and engineering relevance of simulant-based research. In doing so, it would help bridge the gap between planetary science and bulk solids engineering, enabling more robust and defensible development of future lunar surface systems.

3 Overview of terrestrial bulk materials characterisation approaches

In terrestrial industries that routinely handle bulk solids, such as mining, minerals processing, agriculture, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and construction; the systematic characterisation of material properties is a well-established and essential practice [22,23,24]. Reliable material characterisation underpins the design, manufacture, operation, and optimisation of bulk handling systems and is critical for ensuring process efficiency, operational reliability, and safety [25]. Over several decades, this has led to the development of standardised workflows, test methods, and reporting practices that allow engineers to anticipate material behaviour and mitigate operational risks [26, 27,28].

This section provides an overview of the rationale, scope, and methodologies commonly employed in

terrestrial bulk materials characterisation. It first outlines the importance of material characterisation in engineering practice, followed by a structured review of key characterisation approaches. These are grouped into the following categories: (i) physical and chemical properties, (ii) flow properties, (iii) mechanical properties related to handling, (iv) dustiness, and (v) relevant standards and standardisation frameworks. Together, these approaches form the foundation for the design and validation of reliable bulk materials handling systems.

3.1 Importance of bulk materials characterisation

The importance of characterising bulk materials in terrestrial applications arises from several interrelated requirements. Foremost among these is engineering system design. Fundamental material properties, including particle size distribution, bulk density, flowability, shear strength, and compressibility, directly influence the geometry, operating limits, and reliability of handling equipment such as hoppers, silos, feeders, conveyors, and chutes. For example, hopper wall angles and outlet dimensions are explicitly selected based on measured shear strength and flow function data to avoid flow obstructions [27,28].

Beyond initial design, material characterisation enables process optimisation. A detailed understanding of material behaviour allows engineers to refine operating parameters such as feed rates, residence times, mixing conditions, and energy input, thereby improving efficiency and reducing operational costs. This is particularly important in continuous processes, where small mismatches between material behaviour and equipment design can lead to cumulative performance degradation.

Equally critical is the role of characterisation in preventing and mitigating operational issues. Inadequate or incomplete understanding of material properties is a leading cause of handling failures. Standardised characterisation methods are routinely used to predict and address common problems, including:

- **Flow Obstructions:** Cohesive materials may form stable arches (bridging) or narrow flow channels (ratholing) within storage vessels, interrupting discharge. Shear strength measurements and flow function analysis are central to assessing and preventing these phenomena.
- **Segregation:** Differences in particle size, shape, or density can lead to separation during handling and storage, compromising material homogeneity. Particle size distribution and density measurements are key inputs for segregation risk assessment.
- **Dust Generation:** Fine particles may become airborne during handling, posing health hazards, explosion risks, and environmental concerns. Dustiness testing informs the design of containment, ventilation, and filtration systems.
- **Equipment Wear:** Abrasive materials can cause significant wear to handling equipment, reducing service life and increasing maintenance demands. Abrasive testing supports material selection and maintenance planning.
- **Caking and Agglomeration:** Materials susceptible to moisture uptake or consolidation may form stable agglomerates during storage, impeding flow.

Characterisation of moisture sensitivity and caking tendency is therefore essential.

In addition to operational considerations, material characterisation plays a vital role in quality control, enabling verification of incoming raw materials against specifications and monitoring consistency during processing. Finally, it is fundamental to safety management, supporting the identification of hazards such as dust explosibility, poor flow behaviour leading to manual intervention, or excessive equipment wear.

The pervasive reliance on material characterisation in terrestrial bulk-handling industries underscores the need to adopt similarly rigorous approaches when addressing extra-terrestrial granular materials, such as planetary regolith.

3.2 Characterisation methods

The characterisation of bulk materials in terrestrial engineering is inherently multidimensional, reflecting the complex, often non-linear behaviour of granular materials under handling and processing conditions. No single parameter is sufficient to describe bulk behaviour; instead, a combination of physical, chemical, mechanical, and flow-related properties is required to develop a reliable representation of material performance. Importantly, these properties are not independent: variations in particle size, shape, moisture content, or consolidation state can produce disproportionately large changes in bulk behaviour.

In terrestrial practice, characterisation strategies are therefore selected based on the intended handling scenario, balancing predictive capability, practicality, and repeatability. The subsections below describe the principal categories of characterisation methods, with emphasis on their relevance to bulk materials handling applications.

3.2.1 Physical and chemical properties

The physical and chemical properties of a bulk material form the foundational descriptors from which its handling behaviour emerges. Among these properties, particle size distribution (PSD) is widely recognised as one of the most influential parameters governing bulk material performance [29]. PSD directly affects flowability, segregation tendency, permeability, compressibility, and dust generation, with the fine fraction often exerting a disproportionately strong influence on cohesion and airborne dust release.

For coarser, free-flowing granular materials, sieve analysis remains the most commonly used technique for PSD determination, supported by well-established standards such as ASTM D6913 for soils and granular materials, ASTM C136 for aggregates, and ISO 3310 for test sieves. These methods provide robust, mass-based size distributions and are particularly suitable where particles are sufficiently large and cohesion is limited. In contrast, laser diffraction techniques are widely employed for fine powders and materials with wide size distributions. Standardised under ISO 13320, laser diffraction offers rapid, repeatable measurements; however, the results are inherently model-dependent, requiring careful selection of optical parameters and

transparent reporting to ensure meaningful comparisons between datasets.

Where particle morphology deviates significantly from spherical assumptions, dynamic image analysis (DIA) has gained increasing prominence. This technique enables simultaneous measurement of particle size and shape, making it particularly valuable for materials composed of angular or elongated particles. Guidance on the representation, calculation, and reporting of particle size and shape data obtained through image-based techniques is provided by ISO 9276 (Parts 1–6). For very fine particles, sedimentation-based methods, such as hydrometer analysis conducted in accordance with ASTM D422, continue to be used. However, their applicability is limited to cohesive materials and particles with irregular geometries.

Closely linked to particle size is particle shape and morphology, which strongly influence interparticle friction, packing behaviour, and shear resistance. Shape descriptors, including aspect ratio, sphericity, elongation, and angularity, are typically derived from optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), or DIA. While no single standard prescribes a universal method for particle shape characterisation, ISO 9276-6 provides recommended shape descriptors and guidance for their interpretation. In practice, consistency in methodology, imaging conditions, and data processing is essential for meaningful comparisons between studies.

Density measurements provide further insight into the internal structure and packing efficiency of bulk materials. Poured and tapped bulk density describe the material in its loosely poured and mechanically consolidated states, respectively, and are commonly measured in accordance with ASTM D7481 or ISO 3953. These values are frequently used to derive empirical flow indicators such as the Hausner ratio, which, while not a predictive design tool, offers useful comparative insight into flowability and compressibility [30]. In contrast, particle (true) density reflects the intrinsic density of the solid material itself. It is typically measured by gas pycnometry [31] in accordance with ASTM D5550 or ISO 12154, or by liquid-displacement methods standardised under ASTM D854. The relationship between poured, tapped, and particle density values provides a quantitative indication of voidage, consolidation behaviour, and sensitivity to aeration or vibration.

In addition to size, shape, and density, other physical and chemical properties play an important modifying role in bulk handling behaviour. Moisture content, even at low levels, can dramatically increase cohesion and promote caking by forming liquid bridges between particles [32]. Standard methods for moisture determination include oven drying (ASTM E871) and Karl Fischer titration for low-moisture materials [33]. Chemical composition, typically characterised using techniques such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF), inductively coupled plasma spectroscopy (ICP-AES or ICP-MS), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), influences intrinsic properties such as hardness, reactivity, and surface chemistry. Mineralogical composition and crystalline structure, as determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD), also affect particle breakage behaviour, abrasivity, and surface roughness.

Finally, surface area and electrostatic properties are increasingly recognised as important contributors to bulk handling performance, particularly for fine powders [34,35,36]. Specific surface area and porosity influence moisture adsorption, cohesion, and the effectiveness of flow aids. They are commonly measured using gas adsorption techniques based on the BET method (ISO 9277) or by mercury intrusion porosimetry [37]. Electrostatic behaviour, which affects dust generation, powder adhesion, and handling stability in low-humidity environments, is assessed using charge decay, resistivity, and triboelectric testing methods, as outlined in the IEC 61340 series. Taken together, these physical and chemical characterisation techniques provide the essential baseline information required to interpret and predict bulk material behaviour. Their widespread use and standardisation in terrestrial bulk solids engineering establish a robust framework that can be systematically adapted to the characterisation of planetary regolith simulants.

3.2.2 Flow properties

Building upon the fundamental physical descriptors, flow properties capture how a bulk material responds to applied stresses during storage, discharge, and transport. In terrestrial bulk solids engineering, flow behaviour is recognised as inherently stress-dependent and history-dependent, meaning that a material's response is strongly influenced by its consolidation state and handling history. As a result, flow characterisation focuses not only on whether a material flows, but also on the conditions and constraints under which flow can be reliably maintained.

Central to the prediction of flow behaviour is the determination of shear strength, which quantifies the resistance of a bulk material to failure under applied normal stress. Shear strength measurements are most commonly obtained using shear testers [38,39], such as the Jenike shear tester or ring shear testers, following standardised procedures including ASTM D6128. These tests enable the construction of the flow function, which relates unconfined yield strength to consolidation stress and provides a quantitative basis for classifying materials from free flowing to highly cohesive. Parameters such as internal friction angle and cohesion, derived from shear testing, are directly used in the design of hoppers and silos to prevent flow obstructions such as arching and rat-holing [28,40,41].

In parallel with shear testing, a range of simpler, empirical indicators are frequently used to provide rapid insight into flow potential. The angle of repose, defined as the angle formed by a freely poured pile of material, remains one of the most widely reported flow descriptors [42]. Although easy to measure, angle of repose values are highly sensitive to test geometry and procedure, and no single universally adopted standard exists. Consequently, such measurements are typically used for comparative screening rather than as predictive design inputs. Similarly, the Hausner ratio and Carr index, derived from standard pour and tapped bulk density measurements, provide empirical indicators of flowability and compressibility, but lack the stress-dependent resolution required for equipment design [30].

Other flow-related properties address more specific handling phenomena. Permeability, which describes the

ease with which gas passes through a packed bed of material, governs aeration and de-aeration behaviour during filling and discharge. Low permeability can lead to air entrapment and unstable flow, while high permeability may promote fluidisation and dust release. Permeability is typically measured using dedicated airflow or permeability testers, following manufacturer-specific or laboratory-defined protocols, as no single universal standard exists.

Compressibility and consolidation behaviour describe how bulk density and voidage evolve under applied load and are particularly relevant to storage stability and feeder performance. These properties are often assessed using compressibility testers or oedometer-type methods, drawing on soil mechanics standards such as ASTM D2435, where applicable.

Additional flow-related challenges include segregation and caking. Segregation, arising from differences in particle size, shape, or density, is typically evaluated through controlled filling and discharge experiments, followed by spatial sampling and particle-size analysis. While no formal standards govern segregation testing, methodologies are well documented in bulk solids literature [28]. Caking and agglomeration tendency, particularly under prolonged storage or elevated humidity, are assessed through controlled environmental exposure tests followed by measurement of cake strength or disintegration behaviour, often adapted from food and pharmaceutical powder testing practices. Collectively, these flow property measurements provide the foundation for predicting handling performance and identifying potential failure modes.

3.2.3 Mechanical properties related to handling

In addition to flow behaviour, the interaction between bulk materials and handling equipment is governed by mechanical properties related to wear, degradation, and structural integrity under applied stresses. These properties are particularly important for mineral based materials, where repeated handling can lead to progressive equipment damage or material breakdown.

Abrasivity quantifies a bulk material's tendency to wear equipment surfaces and is a critical consideration in the design and maintenance of handling systems [43]. Abrasivity is influenced by particle hardness, angularity, surface roughness, and contact mechanics. Common assessment methods include rotating drum tests, where material tumbles against standardised test coupons, and pin-on-disc or sliding wear tests that measure friction and material loss on test coupons under controlled conditions. While no single, universally adopted standard exists specifically for bulk material abrasivity, relevant guidance is often drawn from tribological standards, such as ASTM G99 for sliding wear, and supplemented by industry-specific practices.

Closely related to abrasivity are friability and attrition, which describe the tendency of particles to fracture, chip, or generate fines during handling operations such as conveying, mixing, and impact loading [44]. Attrition alters particle size distribution over time, often increasing fines content and, consequently, affecting flowability, dustiness, and segregation behaviour. Friability and attrition are typically assessed using controlled impact

tests or tumbling devices, followed by comparison of particle size distributions before and after testing. These methods are widely used in industry, although standards are generally application-specific rather than universal. At the particle scale, hardness provides additional context for both wear and attrition behaviour. Hardness is commonly measured using micro indentation techniques, which quantify resistance to local deformation. While hardness alone does not fully predict bulk degradation behaviour, it serves as an important complementary parameter when interpreting abrasivity and attrition results.

3.2.4 Dustiness

Dustiness characterises the propensity of a bulk material to generate airborne particles during handling and is directly linked to occupational health, safety, and environmental performance [45]. Dust generation is influenced by fines content, interparticle cohesion, electrostatic charging, moisture content, and attrition behaviour. Importantly, dustiness is not an intrinsic material constant but a response to imposed mechanical disturbance.

Standardised dust emissivity tests aim to provide comparative indices of dust release under controlled and repeatable conditions rather than replicating specific industrial processes. Widely recognised methods include the Heubach Dustmeter, in which material is dropped under controlled airflow and airborne dust is collected gravimetrically, and the Rotating Drum Dustiness Tester, where material is tumbled within a rotating enclosure while released dust is extracted and quantified [46]. Procedural guidance and classification approaches for dustiness testing are provided by standards such as VDI 2066 Part 5.

In terrestrial practice, dustiness data are typically used alongside explosion severity testing, ventilation design, and containment strategies. Although dustiness tests do not capture all aspects of process-specific dust generation, they provide a valuable and standardised basis for comparative assessment and risk management.

3.2.5 Relevant standards and standardisation bodies

Standardisation is a cornerstone of reliable and defensible bulk solids characterisation. The adoption of recognised standards for test apparatus, experimental procedures, and data reporting ensures that measured material properties are repeatable, comparable, and transferable across laboratories, institutions, and application domains. In terrestrial bulk materials engineering, such standardisation underpins effective technical communication, supports the development of shared material property databases, and provides engineers with dependable inputs for equipment design, process modelling, and risk assessment.

Where comprehensive standards exist, they establish not only test methodologies but also boundary conditions, sample preparation requirements, and reporting conventions. This reduces ambiguity in interpretation and enables meaningful comparison of datasets generated using different equipment or by different operators. As a result, standardised characterisation data are routinely used to inform high-consequence engineering decisions in

industries where handling failures may lead to safety incidents, production losses, or environmental harm.

However, the landscape of bulk materials characterisation is uneven. While many physical and flow-related properties such as particle size distribution, density, and shear strength are governed by well-established standards, other commonly reported descriptors lack universally adopted test protocols. Properties such as angle of repose, abrasivity, and friability are often measured using a wide range of apparatus configurations and procedures, leading to significant variability in reported values. In such cases, differences in test geometry, applied stress, or data interpretation can obscure genuine material behaviour and limit the reliability of cross-study comparisons. This variability highlights an ongoing need to refine and more widely adopt standardised approaches, particularly for properties that play a critical role in bulk handling performance.

A range of international and national organisations undertake the development and maintenance of standards for bulk materials characterisation. International standards bodies, such as the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) [23] and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) [47], provide globally recognised frameworks that facilitate cross border collaboration and data exchange. National standards organisations, including ASTM International [22] and DIN [DIN Standards Web Page], play a central role in developing detailed test methods that are widely adopted in research and industry. In parallel, engineering and professional associations, such as the Association of German Engineers (VDI) [48], publish technical guidelines that address specific aspects of bulk solids handling, often bridging gaps where formal standards are absent. Collaborative groups and working parties, including those operating under the European Federation of Chemical Engineering (EFCE) [49], further contribute by consolidating industrial experience and promoting best practice.

In many sectors, these formal standards and guidelines are supplemented by industry-specific protocols tailored to particular materials, equipment, or operational contexts. While such practices can be highly effective within a given domain, they may limit broader comparability unless their assumptions and limitations are clearly documented. Consequently, transparent reporting of test conditions, methodology, and data processing remains essential, particularly when standardised methods are not available.

3.3 Summary

This section has reviewed the terrestrial framework for bulk materials characterisation, emphasising the critical role of standardisation in ensuring data quality, comparability, and engineering relevance. The established standards, guidelines, and best practices used in terrestrial industries provide a mature and well-validated foundation for characterising granular materials. This foundation is essential when considering the extension or adaptation of bulk materials handling characterisation approaches to lunar regolith simulants, where reproducibility, transparency, and cross-institutional comparability are

equally vital for the development and validation of future planetary surface systems.

4 Proposed standardised approach to bulk materials handling characterisation of planetary regolith simulants

This section outlines and justifies a suite of standardised experimental techniques and commercially available test equipment for the characterisation of the bulk-materials-handling properties of planetary regolith simulants. Particular emphasis is placed on investigating dynamic bulk behaviour, which is presently underrepresented in the characterisation of regolith simulants but is critical for future surface operations.

The proposed approach is intended to complement existing geotechnical and compositional characterisation practices by incorporating material properties directly relevant to excavation, storage, transport, processing, and construction, especially in the context of future in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) activities on the Moon and planets. All selected techniques are well established in terrestrial bulk solids engineering and rely on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) instrumentation, ensuring accessibility, reproducibility, and inter laboratory comparability. Equipment available at the Wolfson Centre for Bulk Solids Handling Technology at the University of Greenwich and ESA Vulcan Analogue Sample Facility at Harwell Campus was used to test available planetary regolith simulants.

4.1 Particle size distribution analysis of lunar regolith simulants via Laser Light Scattering

The particle size distribution (PSD) of planetary regolith simulants was determined using laser light scattering, employing a Malvern Mastersizer 3000. This technique follows internationally recognised standards, including ISO 13320-1 and ASTM E2651, and provides a robust and repeatable means of characterising particles across a wide size range, from nanometres to millimetres.

This broad measurement capability is essential for capturing the inherently diverse PSD of lunar regolith, which comprises both fine dust and coarser granular fractions. Laser diffraction is particularly advantageous for simulant characterisation as it is non-destructive, preserving the particle structure and enabling subsequent analyses using complementary techniques, an important consideration given the limited availability of high-fidelity simulant materials.

The method is rapid, readily automated, and well-suited to high throughput characterisation, making it appropriate for comparative studies and batch-to-batch quality control. When operated under standardised protocols and with appropriate calibration, laser diffraction provides highly reproducible PSD data across different laboratories. Compared with traditional sieving methods, laser light scattering offers superior sensitivity to fine silt- and clay-sized fractions, which are particularly relevant to lunar dust behaviour, including electrostatic charging, adhesion, and transport phenomena on the lunar surface.

4.2 Particle morphology

The morphological characterisation of lunar regolith simulants was conducted using an automated optical microscope Malvern Morphologi G3SE [50]. This

technique enables direct visualisation and quantitative measurement of individual particle parameters, including length, width, circularity, aspect ratio, convexity, and surface roughness.

The use of automated image analysis allows statistically significant populations of particles to be analysed within a relatively short timeframe, ensuring representative characterisation of bulk simulant batches. Well-defined operating procedures and automated data processing significantly reduce operator bias and enhance reproducibility, which is essential for standardisation across laboratories.

The resulting quantitative morphological data, supported by particle imagery, can be directly compared with high-resolution images and published datasets derived from genuine lunar regolith samples returned by the Apollo missions and other lunar exploration programmes. Automated microscopy also enables identification and quantification of distinct particle populations within regolith simulants such as mineral fragments, agglutinates, and glassy spherules based on their characteristic shapes and textures.

By providing statistically robust morphological descriptors, automated optical microscopy directly contributes to the classification of lunar regolith simulants, enabling an objective assessment of how closely a simulant replicates the shape characteristics of real lunar regolith. This is a critical criterion for high-fidelity simulants. Furthermore, the technique supports batch-to-batch quality control and facilitates systematic comparison of simulants developed by different suppliers or research groups. Morphological data can also be correlated with flowability and electrostatic behaviour, improving understanding of the role of particle shape in governing bulk handling performance.

4.3 Specific gravity (related to particle density)

Particle density, expressed as specific gravity or true density, was measured using a gas pycnometer with a Quantachrome ULTRAPYC 1200 and following established procedures, such as ASTM D854. A gas pycnometer provides a highly accurate and non-reactive method for determining the true volume of solid material, excluding interparticle void space.

This capability is particularly important for lunar regolith particles, which often include porous agglutinates. The use of inert gases (typically helium or nitrogen) ensures that the material remains chemically and physically unaltered during testing, preserving sample integrity. Accurate particle density measurements provide insight into the mineralogical composition of the regolith and support comparison between samples originating from different lunar analogues or geological contexts.

When combined with bulk and tapped density measurements, true density enables the calculation of total porosity, a key parameter that influences mechanical strength, permeability, thermal conductivity, and fluid flow behaviour. Reliable particle density data also underpin mass–volume relationships required for equipment design, storage planning, and construction activities on the Moon. The well-established and standardised nature of gas pycnometer ensures high

reproducibility and makes it well-suited for inclusion in a standardised simulant characterisation protocol.

4.4 Poured and tapped bulk density

Poured and Tapped bulk density measurements were conducted using a Copley JV 2000 [51] tapped density tester, following standards including ASTM D4253, ASTM D4254, and ASTM D7481. Poured bulk density represents the loosest achievable packing state of the simulant, providing a baseline for volume estimation, storage requirements, and initial flow behaviour assessment.

Tapped density simulates densification arising from handling, transport, vibration, and mechanical disturbance. The resulting density reflects more efficient packing state and is relevant for predicting load-bearing capacity, material stability, and storage efficiency in lunar construction and ISRU scenarios. A large difference between pour and tapped bulk density indicates high compressibility and sensitivity to mechanical agitation.

The ratio between these values, commonly expressed as the Hausner ratio, provides an empirical indication of flowability and compressibility. Reporting these parameters using standardised methods enables direct comparison of simulants and supports objective suitability assessment for specific applications.

Although lunar gravity is significantly lower than Earth's, mechanical disturbances arising from equipment operation and astronaut activity are expected to induce localised compaction. Tapped density testing provides a conservative upper bound for density under mechanical agitation, offering a practical laboratory analogue for these effects. The standardised nature of the method enhances reproducibility and supports consistent classification of lunar regolith simulants.

4.5 Flowability data of bulk materials – quasi-static testing

Flowability was characterised using a Brookfield Powder Flow Tester (PFT) [52] in accordance with ASTM D6128. The PFT enables quantitative determination of the yield locus of a consolidated powder bed, which is fundamental for measuring flow obstructions such as arching and rat-holing in storage vessels and feed systems.

The instrument allows direct measurement of the flow function, relating unconfined yield strength to consolidating stress, and provides a basis for classifying powders according to their flow behaviour. This information is critical for the design of reliable handling systems for lunar regolith in ISRU processing, storage, and construction applications.

The PFT also supports time consolidation testing, enabling assessment of how sustained loads affect flow behaviour and indicating susceptibility to caking or hardening during long-term storage. Wall friction measurements against construction and handling materials further inform the design of chutes, hoppers, and conveyors.

Beyond simple flow classification, the PFT provides quantitative values for internal friction, cohesion, bulk density, compressibility, and consolidation behaviour. The use of commercially available COTS equipment enhances accessibility and promotes the adoption of consistent testing protocols across institutions involved in lunar regolith simulant research.

4.6 Flowability data of bulk materials – dynamic testing

As a method to evaluate the dynamic properties of the materials rotating drum is proposed. Unlike quasi-static shear testing, this technique assesses material in continuous flow to quantify dynamic flowability and cohesiveness. The method follows the general principles of ASTM D8648 for assessing dynamic flow regimes. Measurements were performed using a commercially available rotating drum tester GranuDrum from the company Granutools [53].

Three main indices that define the dynamic flowability characteristics of granular materials. The Angle of First Avalanche (α_{static}) marks the onset of motion, indicating the maximum angle reached before the first heap collapse. During steady rotation, the Dynamic Angle of Repose (α_r) represents the average interface angle; higher values indicate lower flowability. Finally, the Cohesiveness Index (CI) quantifies fluctuations in the dynamic angle; higher values indicate stronger inter-particle forces, such as van der Waals or electrostatic interactions, which lead to irregular flow.

This method is vital for ISRU research, where the cohesiveness index identifies the tendency toward agglomeration in rotary kilns. By characterising dynamic flow, designers can predict the reliability of conveyors and processors, ensuring fines and electrostatic proxies are accounted for in hardware designed for lunar gravity environments.

4.7 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provides high-resolution insight into particle morphology, surface texture, and microstructural features of lunar regolith simulants. SEM imaging reveals angularity, surface roughness, presence of agglutinates, and fine dust coatings, all of which influence flow behaviour, abrasion potential, and equipment wear.

SEM is particularly valuable for examining dust agglomerates and particle adhesion mechanisms, informing the design of handling systems and dust mitigation strategies. When combined with image analysis, SEM enables quantitative assessment of micro-scale morphological parameters and supports verification of batch consistency and simulant fidelity relative to genuine lunar regolith.

Although SEM is not a bulk characterisation technique in isolation, it provides essential contextual information that enhances the interpretation of bulk flow and mechanical test results and strengthens the overall robustness of simulant classification.

4.8 Summary

Together, these techniques form a coherent, standardised framework for characterising the bulk-materials-handling behaviour of lunar regolith simulants using established terrestrial methodologies and accessible instrumentation. Their combined application addresses critical gaps in current simulant characterisation practice and provides a defensible basis for evaluating simulant suitability for future lunar surface operations.

5 Common format for inclusion of results/data in appropriate databases

The goal of the proposed data format is to present the acquired data in an accessible and understandable way for the material handling scientific community. The format should allow adding and editing the information.

5.1 Data matrix format presentation

Experimental data are presented in tabular format. This format offers several critical advantages, such as:

- Systematic organisation; providing a logical and compact arrangement of complex data, diagrams, scans and photos into a self-explanatory structure
- Direct comparison: facilitating immediate side-to-side comparison of different planetary regolith simulant samples
- A multiple graphical plot presentation allows for the identification of trends, specifics, and examples for selected materials in one place
- Statistical readiness simplifies additional statistical treatment of sample materials

The first page of the matrix, named General Data, includes all the tested materials collected on a single page. Included are basic information such as the type of planetary regolith simulant, the source or origin of the raw material, and the manufacturer. Included are also the main purpose of the simulant material and the basic flowability level. Attached are also example photographs of regolith samples and three separate diagrams showing fundamental flow characteristics for all the samples in the catalogue, including the included samples. The objective of this page is to provide general data about the tested material, including basic flow properties.

Each material is further outlined in an individual page presentation. On individual pages, general data for the simulant material, including the average Angle of Repose and Average Angle of first avalanche values, are summarised. The next column describes particle properties such as particle size distribution and particle morphology. Bulk properties are outlined in the next column, followed by a representative high-resolution Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image. Below is a graphical presentation of the bulk flow properties and morphological data for the individual sample, including microscope scans of the individual sample grains. At the bottom of the page are presented data obtained from rotating drum tester, providing dynamic angle of repose and cohesiveness index at different RPMs. There is also a remark section for noting guidelines and recommendations for tested materials, describing the main properties, characteristics, and the applications for which the material is suitable.

Within individual simulant material pages, all important material handling properties are presented, and on the basis of this, material's characteristics and handling behaviour are clearly displayed.

6 An approach for community oversight/regulation/standardisation/maintenance

6.1 Online storage and sharing data

As important as the quality of experimentally obtained datasets is the proper online presentation and availability of the data to the general scientific community. The rationale for this selection is to present the bulk material-handling properties of planetary regolith simulants in a suitable scientific data format, easily accessible online for the interested scientific community. A collection of different data objects should be easily understood, maintained and shared. With an estimated large amount of data, it is also important to achieve high performance in accessing and managing data online.

As one of the ready-made solutions that could accommodate extremely large, complex, high-dimensional, and heterogeneous data, the Hierarchical Data Format, version 5 (HDF5), developed by The HDF Group [54], is proposed. The main benefit of HDF5 is a single-file structure with a folder-like hierarchy, making it easy to share.

To optimise computational efficiency, the HDF5 partial access and random retrieval features are leveraged. Through this architecture, individual data records or specific image sections are extracted without loading the entire multi-gigabyte dataset into the computer's active memory. Consequently, delays in data transfer are minimised, and memory usage is significantly reduced during processing."

Other possible solutions for scientific data storage and sharing include netCDF-4 [55], Zarr [56], the Advanced Scientific Data Format (ASDF) [57] and others.

7 Examples of characterisation of planetary regolith simulants with proposed bulk materials handling characterisation techniques

7.1 Selection of planetary regolith simulants for initial characterisation

For the initial characterisation and to test the experimental protocol, eight planetary samples were selected. Selection was pragmatically determined by the availability of sample materials from different research institutions (mainly from the Vulcan ESA Facility, TU Braunschweig and Open University), the variety of material types (Lunar highlands, mare, or polar regions), and material handling characteristics (general purpose or targeted for geotechnical-ISRU applications). In addition, a Martian simulant sample, JSC-Mars 1, was tested. Selected materials with basic descriptions are summarised in Table 1.

As an exemplar material for introducing the developed classification protocol, a NU-LHT-2M Lunar highland simulant [58] was selected, supplied from the Open University Space Laboratory because of its specific bulk material handling characteristics, namely, being cohesive. Data relevant data are presented in Table 2.

Classification data for the other seven tested materials will be included in the Appendix of the document.

7.2 Particle size distribution via laser light scattering

For investigating particle size distribution, a Malvern Mastersizer 3000 instrument (Figure 1) utilising the laser diffraction technique was used. The process is based on the principle that particles passing through a laser beam scatter light at wide angles for smaller particles, while larger particles scatter light at narrow angles relative to the incident beam. The system records the light-scattering pattern, which serves as unique information for that specific particle size distribution. A mathematical model is used to calculate particle size. The final output provides a volume-weighted distribution. Commonly reported as D-values. The D_{10} and connected size value (in micrometres) indicate that 10% of the sample volume is smaller than this value.

For the specific sample material NU-LHT-2M, the determined size distribution is as follows: D_{10} - 2 μm , D_{50} - 5 μm , and D_{90} - 22 μm , with a span of 4. It means that only 10% of the material volume consists of particles smaller than 2 μm . The median particle size is 5 μm ; half of the sample volume is comprised of particles smaller than this value, and 90% of the sample volume is below 22 μm . The span of 4 indicates a relatively broad distribution.

Figure 1: Malvern Mastersizer 3000 at Wolfson Centre for Bulk Handling Technology Laboratory (University of Greenwich)

Particle size distribution provides critical insight into the physical and mechanical properties of the tested NU-LHT-2-M simulant material. Because the D_{50} is so low (5 μm), inter-particle forces (such as Van der Waals forces) will dominate over gravity. This indicates the material will be cohesive, prone to clumping, and likely difficult to flow through small apertures. Furthermore, fine particles suggest an immense total surface area per unit of mass. This indicates high chemical reactivity and a significant potential for the dust to adhere to surfaces, such as space suit fabrics or mechanical seals. A D_{90} of 22 μm places nearly the entire sample within the respirable or environmentally hazardous range for mechanical hardware. Indicating this material is effectively a dust simulant, specifically designed to test the limits of filtration and dust-mitigation technologies. The span of 4 suggests that while the particles are fine, there is enough variation in size to allow for relatively high packing density, as smaller particles (D_{10}) can fill the voids

between the larger grains (D_{90}). The granulometric profile indicates a highly cohesive material dominated by fine-grained dust fragments.

7.3 Particle morphology via automatic optical microscopy

The particle shape characteristics were measured using the Static Automated Imaging tool - Malvern Morphologi G3SE (Figure 2). In the study of planetary regolith simulants, this technique serves as a reference standard, providing size and shape (morphology) data for the multiple grains in the test sample. The system operates through a separate four-stage process. Initially, samples are dispersed using the Sample Dispersion Unit (SDU), ensuring the particles are spread out individually and do not overlap. The glass plate with the sample is placed on the motorised stage, which moves in a raster pattern under the microscope objective. At the same time, a high-resolution camera captures multiple photos of individual grains within the sample. The software identifies particles and, from multiple 2D photos, estimates a 3D volume. In the last stage, every particle is measured for multiple parameters, which are compiled into a tabular matrix. The gained data include particle size distributions, particle circularity, particle elongation, and particle convexity for each sample.

For the NU-LHT-2M sample, we determined the average grain circularity to be 0,807, indicating highly non-spherical particle geometry. An average elongation value of 0,336 suggests that a significant portion of the sample consists of non-equant particles. It indicates a high concentration of acicular needle like fragments. The average aspect ratio of 0,664 indicates that the particles in the sample are moderately non-spherical. This value suggests that, on average, the width of the particle is approximately two-thirds of their length. In the context of lunar highland simulants, this score reflects a population of grains that are significantly elongated or flattened rather than cubic or spherical. Based on morphology parameters, we can conclude that combined metrics indicate a material that is prone to mechanical resistance and flow instability, including mechanical interlocking, stable arch formation, anisotropic flow, and high porosity and compressibility.

Figure 2: Malvern Morphologi G3SE at Wolfson Centre for Bulk Handling Technology Laboratory (University of Greenwich)

7.4 Particle and bulk density measurements

Particle density was determined by measuring particle volume and combining the results with gravimetric analysis. Well-established technique of gas pycnometer was used to determine particle volume via gas displacement and the pressure/volume relationship given by Boyle's Law for a sample in a sealed chamber. An Ultrapyc1200 nitrogen gas pycnometer produced by Quantachrome (now owned by Anton Paar, Austria) was used for the laboratory tests (Figure 3). Particle density values are presented in Table 2 within a section Bulk property.

Figure 3: Gas Pycnometer Ultrapyc1200 at Wolfson Centre for Bulk Handling Technology Laboratory (University of Greenwich)

The loose-poured bulk density and tapped bulk density results of the materials were obtained using the tapped density tester (Copley JV 2000) (Figure 4), performing 1250 taps on the specific sample volume under laboratory conditions, following the ASTM D7481 standard protocol. Results are presented in Table 2.

For the selected NU-LHT-2 M lunar simulant, the particle density was determined as 2964 kg/m³, whereas the tapped and bulk density values are 877 kg/m³ and 1293 kg/m³, respectively.

Experimental values indicates that NU-LHT-2M lunar simulant is cohesive and compressible, characterised by a Hausner Ratio of around 1.5 which indicates very poor flowability. The massive gap between its loose bulk density (877 kg/m³) and particle density (2964 kg/m³) means the material is roughly 70% void space and will settle significantly under vibration. In a handling environment, this material is likely to bridge or rathole in hoppers, requiring mechanical vibrators or steep discharge angles to prevent clogging. While the material is low-density in its loose bulk state, the high density of individual grains suggests it will be highly abrasive to equipment

Figure 4: Tapped density tester (Copley JV 2000) with JSC Mars-1 sample at Wolfson Centre for Bulk Handling Technology Laboratory (University of Greenwich)

7.5 Particle flow measurements via ring-shear testing

Particle flow measurements were performed with a commercially available rotational shear cell tester - Brookfield Powder Flow Tester (PFT) manufactured by AMETEK Brookfield Engineering Laboratories, Inc., Middleboro, MA, USA (Figure 5), following the ASTM D6128 standard.

A test sample with a standard volume of 30mL to 230 mL (giving a mass of the sample between 50g and 200g) is poured into the annular cell and levelled off to ensure a uniform surface. The cell is placed on the rotating shear tester drive unit, and a vane lid is lowered onto the sample. The tester applies a specific downward force (normal stress) and rotates the cell until the powder reaches a steady state. This simulates how the powder is packed at the bottom of a silo or hopper. This presents consolidation point. Once consolidated, the machine performs a series of failure tests. This is achieved by reducing the normal stress and allowing the cell to rotate slowly until the powder material breaks (shears). The maximum torque required to cause the break is recorded. This procedure is repeated 3 to 5 times at different (lower) normal stresses to create a Mohr Circle plot. The flow function is determined, including the material cohesion, effective internal friction angle, compaction curve, and effective angle of wall friction.

Figure 5: Brookfield Powder Flow Tester (PFT) at Wolfson Centre for Bulk Handling Technology Laboratory (Greenwich University)

From the Flow Function Curves (Table 2), it can be determined that the NU-LHT-2M is cohesive to very cohesive [28]. The effective angles of internal friction (starting at 58 deg.) and wall friction (starting at 37 deg. and staying above 30 deg. even at higher stress) are the highest among all tested samples. The experimental data suggest that an effective silo or hopper design would require steep walls. The tested material is very prone to funnel flow and rat-holing. It is highly possible that, for establishing an efficient flow, an additional energy source in the form of a vibration device would be needed, and gravity release of the material from a silo- or hopper-like geometry is not expected. High friction values usually also correlate with angular, jagged particle shapes, resulting in high abrasiveness and highly cohesive, contaminant-prone characteristics.

The steep compaction curve for NU-LHT-2M material indicates high compressibility, resulting in poor flow characteristics and vulnerability to clogging.

Measurements performed with the ring shear flow tester all indicate a poor flowability characteristic of the NU-LHT-2M sample material.

7.6 Dynamic flowability characteristics measurements via rotating drum tester

Dynamic flowability characterisation was performed with a commercially available GranuDrum tester [GranuDrum web Page] (Figure 6), manufactured by Granutools at ESA Vulcan Harwell facilities.

A cylinder is partially filled with 55mL (50% volume) and rotated at controlled speeds. Two sets of tests, each with three repetitions, were performed for individual tested material. The first set of measurements, called speed hysteresis, was used to determine the dynamic angle of repose and cohesiveness index for the tested materials at different rotation speeds, typically in intervals from 2 to 60 RPMs, initially increasing and subsequently decreasing to perform a hysteresis measurement.

With another test method, the angle of the first avalanche was determined. Ten measurements with the

drum rotation speed at 0,5 RPM were averaged to determine the value of the inclination angle when the sample starts to slide. All measurements were performed under laboratory conditions at ESA Vulcan facilities following the standard ASTM D8648 test protocol.

Figure 6: GranuDrum tester, same as used for tests at ESA Vulcan facilities at Harwell (Copyright: Granutools)

The middle (second) measurement out of three is presented in the result matrix.

The dynamic flowability analysis of the NU-LHT-2M lunar highland simulant, composed of high-calcium plagioclase, dunite, and specific mineral additives, reveals a material characterised by high internal friction and significant cohesive behaviour.

Across the tested speed range, the material exhibited a high Dynamic Angle of Repose of 45°-75°, consistent with the highly angular and irregular morphology of its particles. Furthermore, the Cohesiveness index (CI) remained consistently elevated across the full speed range, typically fluctuating between 30 and 60. These high values for the Dynamic Angle of Repose and Cohesiveness index indicate a poorly flowing, highly cohesive material, dominated by strong interparticle forces that prevent the formation of a smooth, continuous rolling bed. Notably, the hysteresis loop analysis showed negligible thixotropy (the property of becoming less viscous under applied shear stress), as the overlap between the increasing and decreasing speed curves suggests that the cohesive structures are not permanently disrupted by shear. For ISRU applications, these results predict a high risk of intermittent avalanching and clogging in gravity fed systems and suggest that mechanical agitation may not significantly improve the flow consistency of this simulant. The average Angle of First Avalanche was measured at approximately 30°, indicating a relatively stable initial structure that requires a distinct energy threshold to initiate motion.

Simulant name	Sample	SEM Image	Provider	Type	Origin	Purpose
JSC Mars-1		NASA (JSC) Johnson Space Centre (JSC) 1998	Martian regolith general purpose (Spectral Analogue)	Palagonitic tephra	Spectral calibration, agricultural experiments, dust mitigation tests	
NU-LHT-2M		NASA, U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), Zybek Advanced Products	Lunar highlands simulant	High calcium plagioclase, dunite and additives	Geotechnical and mobility testing, ISRU, instrument calibration	
TUBS-M		Institute of Space Systems (IRAS), TU Brunswick (Germany)	Lunar mare simulant	Alkali-olivine basalt	ISRU, manufacturing, geotechnical testing, dust research	
TUBS-T		Institute of Space Systems (IRAS), TU Brunswick (Germany)	Lunar highlands simulant	Metamorphosed gabbroic complex (anorthosite)	Lunar infrastructure and construction, 3D printing, and laser sintering techniques	
EAC-1		European Astronaut Centre (EAC) (EU)	Lunar mare simulant	Basanite	Astronaut training, mobility and robotics, ISRU, dust mitigation tests	
LHS-1		CLASS Exolith Lab at the University of Central Florida (USA)	Lunar highlands simulant	Anorthosite, basalt, ilmenite, pyroxene, olivine	Geomechanical and engineering testing, ISRU, plume effects interaction	
LMS-1		CLASS Exolith Lab at the University of Central Florida (USA)	Lunar mare simulant	Pyroxene and glass-rich basalt, anorthosite, ilmenite, olivine	ISRU research, sintering and 3D printing, geotechnical hardware testing	
LSP-2		CLASS Exolith Lab at the University of Central Florida (USA)	Lunar south pole simulant	Anorthosite, glass-rich basalt	Artemis mission planning, ISRU, thermal testing, mobility, trafficability testing	

Table 1: Selection of the tested materials with basic descriptions, including 500µm scale resolution SEM image

General		Particle properties				Bulk properties		SEM Image					
Sample name	NU LHT-2M	Particle size		Morphology		Particle density (kg/m3)	2964						
Type of simulant	Lunar highlands	D10	2	Shape factors		Poured bulk density (kg/m3)	877						
Source/ Origin	Calcium plagioclase	D50	5	Circularity	0,807	Tapped bulk density (kg/m3)	1293						
Manufacturer/ Provider	NASA, USGS, Zybek	D90	22	Elongation	0,336	Porosity (%)	70,4						
Purpose/ Intended use	Geotechnical, Mobility	Span	4	Aspect Ratio	0,664	Compressibility Index (CI)	32,2						
Average AoR	55,8					Hausner Ratio (HR)	1,5						
Averag.Angl. of first aval.	29,9					Classification on basis of CI	Very Poor						
						Classification on basis of HR	Very Poor						
Bulk flow properties				Morphological data - particle shape distribution									
Rotating drum tests		RPM	02	04	06	08	10	20	30	40	50	60	Guidelines and recommendations
Dynamic angle (deg.)	UP		62,4	72,4	60,5	62,6	58,9	53,2	46,3	59,4	58,1	52,0	
	DOWN		62,4	59,9	67,5	71,4	55,5	64,2	58,9	50,0	48,2	52,9	
Cohesivnes index	UP		42,9	39,9	51,8	47,4	50,1	35,8	32,1	35,7	32,8	34,4	
	DOWN		46,9	46,8	45,5	45,0	56,8	42,6	42,1	38,7	53,3	34,0	

Table 2: Example of a matrix table for sample NU-LHT-2M

7.7 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

In the characterisation of granular material flowability, the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) serves as an important visual validation tool. While automatic optical microscopy, such as Malvern Morphology G3SE, provides statistical morphological parameters, SEM scans of the NU-LHT-2M reveal high surface rugosity and the presence of microasperities, providing a physical explanation for the mechanical interlocking and high internal friction observed in the bulk flow tests, for SEM samples were attached on a carbon tab and coated with gold using an EMITech K575X (Lewes, UK) sputter coater. The samples were examined on a Hitachi SU8030 FEG-SEM (Tokyo, Japan) [59] at an accelerating voltage of 1 kV using secondary electrons.

For each sample, multiple different resolution scans (from 5 to 1000 μ m) including size indication for main features.

Within the matrix presentation, a single SEM scan with 500 μ m scale resolution is included.

8 Proposed route forward for standardised classification of planetary regolith simulants

The progression from a proposed classification framework to a globally adopted standard necessitates extensive community engagement and the establishment of a collaborative data infrastructure. The proposed matrix is not intended to be a static document, but a dynamic repository augmented by contributions from the broader lunar and planetary science communities.

By engaging researchers, simulant developers, and mission engineers to contribute their characterisation data, the library of tested samples across diverse regolith analogues can be rapidly extended. This crowdsourced approach will further facilitate the cross-validation of measurement techniques and ensure the matrix remains representative of the evolving landscape of simulant production.

Ultimately, this collective effort bridges the gap between individual laboratory findings and a unified, standardised database, providing the high-fidelity insights required for the success of future In-Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU) and surface exploration missions.

Furthermore, this roadmap places significant emphasis on community education and the systematic upskilling of personnel in the complexities of bulk materials handling. Because planetary regolith simulants pose unique rheological and geomechanical challenges, this standardised classification provides a pedagogical framework to transition the community toward a more rigorous, quantitative understanding of material behaviour. Through this initiative, users are empowered to accurately predict flow characteristics and mechanical responses, which are critical to the success of hardware interfaces. This standardised technical documentation is intended to serve as a foundational tool for professional development, ensuring that the specialised literacy required for the handling and processing of extra-terrestrial analogues is cultivated across the scientific and engineering sectors.

The establishment of community accepted practices and standardised analytical techniques is considered a fundamental objective of this work. Through the introduction of the proposed methodology, a unified approach to regolith characterisation is provided, ensuring that data generated across different laboratories remains inter-comparable and reproducible. It is anticipated that these standardised protocols will be integrated into the operational workflows of specialised research environments, such as the ESA Vulcan facilities and other global planetary analogue centres. By adopting these shared methodologies, the technical requirements for simulant validation can be unified, thereby streamlining collaborative efforts between space agencies, academic institutions, and industrial partners. This alignment ensures that the results of ground-based research are directly applicable to the development of robust flight hardware and lunar surface operations.

9 Conclusions

The successful implementation of lunar and planetary surface operations, particularly those involving In-Situ Resource Utilisation (ISRU), is fundamentally dependent on a precise understanding of regolith bulk handling properties. As demonstrated in this work, the current fragmentation in characterisation methodologies limits the transferability of experimental data and introduces uncertainty into engineering design. To address this, a structured framework for the standardised characterisation of planetary regolith simulants has been proposed and validated.

Through the investigation of test techniques and the testing of eight distinct simulant samples, this study has established a reliable methodology for quantifying the parameters governing the flowability of regolith bulk materials. The development of a standardised data matrix provides a clear, graphical presentation format that ensures results are intercomparable across different research facilities worldwide. The work effectively bridges the gap between planetary science and bulk solids engineering, offering a unified platform for simulant qualification.

The path forward for this framework relies on its adoption as a living standard. By fostering extensive community engagement, providing a basis for specialised training in materials handling, and integrating these accepted practices into research, institutional and industrial workflows. Ultimately, adopting these standards will reduce mission risk and enhance the fidelity of ground-based testing, providing a more predictable foundation for future exploration beyond Earth.

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Appendix

General		Particle properties				Bulk properties		SEM Image
Sample name	JSC Mars-1	Particle size		Morphology		Particle density (kg/m ³)	1793,4	
Type of simulant	Martian general	D10	91	Shape factors		Poured bulk density (kg/m ³)	775	
Source/ Origin	Palagonitic tephra	D50	241	Circularity	0,782	Tapped bulk density (kg/m ³)	905	
Manufacturer/ Provider	NASA JSC	D90	457	Elongation	0,271	Porosity (%)	56,8	
Purpose/ Intended use	General purpose	Span	1,52	Aspect Ratio	0,729	Compressibility Index (CI)	14,4	
Average AoR	23,8					Hausner Ratio (HR)	1,2	
Averag.Angl. of first aval.	/					Classification on basis of CI	Good	
						Classification on basis of HR	Fair	

Bulk flow properties | **Morphological data - particle shape distribution**

Rotating drum tests	RPM	02	04	06	08	10	20	30	40	50	60	Guidelines and recommendations
		Dynamic angle (deg.)	UP	37,1	37,8	43,5	45,7	47,4	44,7	52,7	59,2	
	DOWN	38,0	37,2	44,0	45,5	47,2	42,8	53,1	58,7	64,1	67,6	
Cohesives index	UP	4,7	4,0	4,8	5,8	6,3	5,7	5,6	6,8	15,3	8,8	
	DOWN	4,1	3,8	5,0	5,7	6,4	5,6	8,0	14,9	10,1	9,2	

General		Particle properties			Bulk properties		SEM Image
Sample name	EAC-1	Particle size	Morphology		Particle density (kg/m ³)	1980,4	
Type of simulant	Lunar mare simulant	D10	11	Shape factors	Poured bulk density (kg/m ³)	1400	
Source/ Origin	Basanite	D50	169	Circularity	Tapped bulk density (kg/m ³)	1554	
Manufacturer/ Provider	EAC (ESA)	D90	420	Elongation	Porosity (%)	29,3	
Purpose/ Intended use	Astro. tr./mobility/ ISRU	Span	2,42	Aspect Ratio	Compressibility Index (CI)	10,3	
Average AoR	45				Hausner Ratio (HR)	1,1	
Averag.Angl. of first aval.	31,3				Classification on basis of CI	Good	
					Classification on basis of HR	Free-Flow.	

Usc-SUB030 1.0kV 21.7mm x100.127mm LML 500um

Bulk flow properties | **Morphological data - particle shape distribution**

Rotating drum tests	RPM	02	04	06	08	10	20	30	40	50	60	Guidelines and recommendations
	Dynamic angle (deg.)	UP	50,7	55,0	56,4	50,0	52,9	48,4	47,8	44,3	39,3	
	DOWN	52,7	52,8	49,5	50,0	48,5	45,3	44,5	40,7	40,9	40,3	
Cohesivnes index	UP	20,5	23,7	30,0	28,3	27,2	20,7	11,2	8,3	6,3	4,8	
	DOWN	21,9	24,3	25,3	24,9	23,7	18,3	10,3	7,3	5,6	4,2	

General		Particle properties				Bulk properties		SEM Image
Sample name	LHS-1	Particle size		Morphology	Particle density (kg/m ³)	3228,2		
Type of simulant	Lunar highlands	D10	15	Shape factors	Poured bulk density (kg/m ³)	1280		
Source/ Origin	Anorthosite/ Basalt	D50	101	Circularity	0,862	Tapped bulk density (kg/m ³)	1420	
Manufacturer/ Provider	(CLASS)Exolith Lab/UCF	D90	330	Elongation	0,343	Porosity (%)	60,3	
Purpose/ Intended use	Geomech./ Enginer. tests	Span	3,12	Aspect Ratio	0,657	Compressibility Index (CI)	10,3	
Average AoR	37,8					Hausner Ratio (HR)	1,1	
Averag.Angl. of first aval.	25,3					Classification on basis of CI	Good	
						Classification on basis of HR	Free-Flow.	

Bulk flow properties | **Morphological data - particle shape distribution**

Rotating drum tests	RPM	02	04	06	08	10	20	30	40	50	60	Guidelines and recommendations
	Dynamic angle (deg.)	UP	51,3	46,9	52,2	55,7	52,3	47,7	42,1	45,1	50,3	
	DOWN	52,8	49,6	50,3	47,6	52,3	40,8	44,4	47,6	51,6	49,4	
Cohesivnes index	UP	24,8	23,8	23,7	30,4	24,9	24,1	19,5	14,5	11,3	9,1	
	DOWN	20,2	21,7	26,9	23,1	26,5	24,8	19,8	13,2	11,8	9,9	

General		Particle properties				Bulk properties		SEM Image								
Sample name	LSP-2	Particle size		Morphology	Particle density (kg/m ³)	2530,1										
Type of simulant	Lunar south pole	D10	12	Shape factors	Poured bulk density (kg/m ³)	1530										
Source/ Origin	Anorthosite/ Basalt	D50	143	Circularity	0,869	Tapped bulk density (kg/m ³)		1621								
Manufacturer/ Provider	Exolith Lab/ UCF	D90	395	Elongation	0,337	Porosity (%)		39,5								
Purpose/ Intended use	Artemis/ ISRU/ mobility	Span	2,68	Aspect Ratio	0,663	Compressibility Index (CI)		5,6								
Average AoR	31,5					Hausner Ratio (HR)		1,1								
Averag.Angl. of first aval.	29,4					Classification on basis of CI		Free-Flow.								
						Classification on basis of HR		Free-Flow.								
Bulk flow properties				Morphological data - particle shape distribution												
				<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Record Number</th> <th>Sample Name</th> <th>Unclassified</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>17</td> <td>LSP-2</td> <td>911514</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Totals</td> <td></td> <td>911514</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Record Number	Sample Name	Unclassified	17	LSP-2	911514	Totals		911514
Record Number	Sample Name	Unclassified														
17	LSP-2	911514														
Totals		911514														
Rotating drum tests		RPM	02	04	06	08	10	20	30	40	50	60	Guidelines and recommendations			
Dynamic angle (deg.)		UP	52,8	53,6	54,3	60,0	56,8	66,3	71,3	67,7	64,9	60,3				
		DOWN	53,2	48,3	56,6	59,4	62,2	65,0	68,0	66,9	64,1	63,3				
Cohesivnes index		UP	18,2	20,5	24,1	24,5	25,6	27,4	26,6	27,4	22,2	23,9				
		DOWN	18,7	19,1	26,6	22,9	25,0	33,5	27,1	25,2	26,7	26,6				

General		Particle properties				Bulk properties		SEM Image								
Sample name	LMS-1	Particle size		Morphology	Particle density (kg/m ³)	2800,5										
Type of simulant	Lunar mare simulant	D10	17	Shape factors	Poured bulk density (kg/m ³)	1630										
Source/ Origin	Basalt/Anorthosite/Ilmenite	D50	240	Circularity	0,878	Tapped bulk density (kg/m ³)		1727								
Manufacturer/ Provider	(CLASS)Exolith Lab/UCF	D90	461	Elongation	0,318	Porosity (%)		41,8								
Purpose/ Intended use	ISRU/ sintering/ 3D printing	Span	1,85	Aspect Ratio	0,682	Compressibility Index (CI)		5,9								
Average AoR	29					Hausner Ratio (HR)		1,1								
Averag.Angl. of first aval.	26,8					Classification on basis of CI		Free-Flow.								
						Classification on basis of HR		Free-Flow.								
Bulk flow properties				Morphological data - particle shape distribution												
				<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Record Number</th> <th>Sample Name</th> <th>Unclassified</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>19</td> <td>LMS-1</td> <td>817241</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Totals</td> <td></td> <td>817241</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Record Number	Sample Name	Unclassified	19	LMS-1	817241	Totals		817241
Record Number	Sample Name	Unclassified														
19	LMS-1	817241														
Totals		817241														
Rotating drum tests		RPM	02	04	06	08	10	20	30	40	50	60	Guidelines and recommendations			
Dynamic angle (deg.)	UP		48,6	47,1	50,9	49,4	52,6	65,9	70,2	70,9	68,0	62,2				
	DOWN		48,5	47,3	49,8	50,3	52,5	64,9	71,6	72,2	67,5	64,1				
Cohesivnes index	UP		16,9	14,2	17,9	18,9	23,5	27,7	24,8	25,7	25,4	21,5				
	DOWN		14,7	12,5	22,8	18,1	25,8	27,2	25,3	24,6	26,3	23,4				